

CURRENT TASKS OF FORMING AN IDEAL LEADER MODEL

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ANNOTATION

This article emphasizes that in order to form a modern leader and improve his social image, it is not enough to rely on the significant experience accumulated in this field in the country, it is necessary to form an ideal leader model, search for young, promising specialists with leadership skills, teach them leadership culture, and improve their leadership skills. Therefore, it is scientifically analyzed that without identifying these tasks and ensuring their systematic solution, it is impossible to find a modern leader who would serve the development of the country and the interests of the Motherland.

Basic conceptions: professional mobility, social mobility, modern leader, social image of the leader, ideal leader, democratic management methods, nomenclature of reserve personnel, "mentor-student" system, "young leader", "professional skills", intellectual, moral, legal, political and other characteristics and qualities.

To form a modern leader and improve his social image, it is not enough to rely on the significant experience accumulated in this field in the country, of course. At the same time, it is also necessary to identify urgent tasks that need to be solved in the near future, and to determine measures for their practical implementation. Without identifying these tasks and ensuring their systematic solution, it is impossible to find a modern leader who would serve the development of the country and the interests of the Motherland.

Based on the analysis, we believe that the urgent tasks in Uzbekistan in terms of improving the social image of a modern and ideal leader should be as follows:

To improve the social image of a modern leader, it is necessary to form an ideal leader model and make it a reference point and beacon for efforts in this regard. The ideal leader model refers to a set of knowledge and skills, character and virtues, talents and abilities necessary to manage a company or organization. Scientific considerations and ideas about it have not yet appeared. Many significant ideas have been put forward in the history of socio-philosophical thought in this regard. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr Al-Farabi believes that a leader should naturally embody 12 qualities and virtues: 1) health; 2) prudence; 3) strong memory; 4) intelligence; 5) eloquence; 6) striving for enlightenment; 7) curbing the ego; 8) loving the truth; 9) generosity; 10) not chasing after wealth; 11) justice; 12) determination and courage. We can find similar ideas in the works of Confucius, Al-Mawardi, Ibn al-Azraq, Al-Ghazzali, Nizamul-mulk, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi and others. Similar ideas and considerations are also contained in the heritage of many prominent representatives of Western philosophy.

Today, the scientific ideas of specialists about the ideal leader model are characterized by their diversity. In particular, the Russian scientist A. Kitov, who has specially studied this aspect of the problem, imagines the ideal leader model as a composition consisting of four parts (management skills, political qualities, professional qualities, organizational qualities). Each part, in turn, embodies a number of elements. 1

The First President of our country, Islam Karimov, also thought a lot about the main characteristics of a modern leader and the ways to form these characteristics.

His many speeches expressed significant thoughts on this issue. In particular, in his speech at the IX session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, where the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” and the “National Program for Personnel Training” were adopted, he emphasized: “The achievement of our great goals and noble intentions, the renewal of our society, the development and prospects of our life, the reforms being carried out, the fate of the results of our plans - all this is, first of all, closely connected with the problem of training highly qualified, conscious specialists who meet the requirements of the time.”² The ideal model of such a leadership cadre, according to Islam Karimov, should embody talent, research, possession of modern knowledge, patriotism, loyalty to the country, dedication, skill, independent worldview, faith and beliefs, and similar characteristics.

Scientific ideas about the ideal leadership model are not just a collection of ideas of theoretical importance. On the contrary, the creation of this model will allow to fulfill a number of practical tasks. In particular, without its formation, it is impossible to give purpose, content and orientation to the work on training modern leaders in the country. The existence of such a model would allow to determine specific tasks for the upbringing of modern leaders, to describe in detail the knowledge and abilities, character and virtues, qualifications and skills that need to be formed, to accurately identify shortcomings in the spiritual image of a specific leader. This model serves as a theoretical and methodological basis for the formation of a leader who can serve the development of the Motherland, the prosperity of the country, national interests, and subordinate his activities to the interests of society as a whole. In order to form an ideal leader model, it is necessary, first of all, to conduct scientific research on this topic. Philosophers, political scientists, and educators of our country have carried out and are carrying out numerous scientific research works on the activities of leaders and leadership. However, most of them provide general considerations about the spiritual image of a leader, analyze various problems related to leadership activities. Of course, the facts and arguments presented in these sources, as well as the conclusions drawn, are of great scientific, theoretical and practical importance.

At the same time, it would be expedient to clearly define the ideal leader model. This task can only be accomplished within the framework of special scientific research. Such scientific research can only be carried out on the basis of orders from competent organizations.

Secondly, in order to avoid national narrowness in the formation of the ideal leader model and, based on it, in raising the social image of a modern leader, it is expedient to study and analyze world experience on the subject, especially the achievements of developed countries and influential corporations and companies operating in them. The study of foreign experience would allow raising the social image of a leader not only on the basis of national, but also universal values. This research also requires a certain social order from the government.

1. In order to raise the social image of a modern leader, it is necessary to further improve the mechanism for selecting, educating and improving the skills of leading personnel operating in the country. The social significance of this mechanism is immeasurable. The solution to various social problems in any society directly depends on the activities of the leader, the level of formation of his social image. If a leader organizes his activities on the basis of democratic management methods, his social image is based on universal human values and humanistic ideas, and is not disconnected from real life, he will be able to quickly grasp the causes and consequences of problems in society, the need and ways to eliminate them. The activities of a leader whose social image is fraught with various vices and shortcomings will also be ineffective.

That is why it is necessary for society to have an effective mechanism for selecting, educating and improving the skills of leadership personnel. This mechanism serves to enhance the social image of the leader.

A unique system for selecting leadership personnel was formed during the years of independence. In particular, as we noted in the previous paragraphs, there is a nomenclature of reserve personnel for all prestigious positions, and centers and training courses are operating to familiarize reserve personnel with the secrets of modern leadership. An integrated system is in place that allows most personnel working in leadership positions to continuously improve their skills.

However, it is important to remember that the effectiveness of this mechanism is not a quality that can be achieved with one-time efforts. As various aspects of social life change, this mechanism must also be continuously improved. In order to develop the mechanism for selecting, educating, and improving the skills of leaders in line with modern requirements, it is necessary, first of all, to identify and eliminate existing problems in this regard.

In world science, there are many sources, ideas, concepts, and proposals on the theoretical and methodological foundations of monitoring the process of forming modern leaders. They offer many ways, methods and methods, factors and means of analyzing the effectiveness of the process of training leading personnel in the country.

Of course, the issue is approached based on the socio-political, economic and spiritual situation prevailing in different countries. However, in all of them, when analyzing the process of training managerial personnel, it is emphasized that it is necessary to determine the effectiveness of activities in the following three areas:

a) the effectiveness of measures taken to identify personnel with leadership abilities; any process aimed at training managerial personnel begins with the identification of capable and potential personnel. The effective organization of this process is a prerequisite for providing society with qualified leaders. The effectiveness of measures in this area is associated with the development of clear criteria for determining managerial abilities;

b) the effectiveness of the process of training selected reserve personnel for leadership positions; This process should be aimed not only at expanding the range of knowledge related to the specialty, but also at teaching the secrets of modern management, forming the skills to use information and communication technologies, and developing the ability to adapt one's work to social needs. The effectiveness of measures in this direction depends on ensuring the balance between the process of training reserve personnel and the functional tasks of the position that this personnel must perform;

c) the effectiveness of the process of appointing personnel trained for management to managerial positions; the failure of personnel selected using a special methodology and prepared to occupy a managerial position to remain unassigned to such a position undermines the authority of the entire management training system, as well as the nomenclature of reserves for managerial positions. To prevent this, it is necessary to strictly monitor the process of forming a clear list of vacant managerial positions and filling them, as well as the state of vertical and horizontal professional mobility of managerial personnel.

The conclusion is that in order to form a modern leader in our country and improve his social image, it is necessary to identify urgent tasks that need to be solved in the near future, and to determine measures for their implementation in practice. Social reality analysis shows that

urgent tasks in this regard are related to the formation of an ideal leader model, improving the mechanism for selecting, educating and improving the skills of leaders, searching for young specialists, implementing innovative forms of regular certification of leaders, modernizing the monitoring of the process of training leaders, and determining the goals and objectives of personnel policy in proportion to social processes. The implementation of these tasks creates a solid foundation for improving the social image of leaders.

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